

Introduction to Subfactors. V. Jones and V. S. Sunder. London Mathematical Society, Lecture Notes Series 234, Cambridge University Press. 1997. 162 + xii pp. ISBN 0-521-58420-5, paperback.

V. Jones was awarded the Fields Medal in 1990 for a series of astonishing discoveries in the field of operator algebras. He pioneered the theory of subfactors and demonstrated that this theory has significant implications for many other parts of mathematics. For example, based on his theory he came up with new polynomial invariants for knots. The book under review is a friendly invitation to subfactor theory by two well-known masters of this flourishing field.

Von Neumann algebras are weakly closed *-subalgebras of the algebra of all bounded operators on a Hilbert space. One may also think of them as commutants of ranges of unitary representations of groups. Among von Neumann algebras those with trivial centres are known as *factors*. In view of a well-established decomposition theory, factors are to be thought of as building blocks for other von Neumann algebras.

Murray and von Neumann broadly classified factors into three classes known as types I, II and III, by looking at projections contained in them. A type I factor is isomorphic to the algebra of all bounded operators on a Hilbert space. The dimension of such a Hilbert space becomes an invariant for the factor. Surprisingly this notion of dimension can be extended to type II factors as well, but now the dimension is not necessarily an integer and in fact it can be any positive real number (or infinity). This possibility of 'continuous dimension' interested von Neumann. Jones went a step further. He tried to classify inclusions of factors and discovered that there is a strange mixture of the discrete and the continuous.

Suppose N, M are two type II factors such that N is contained in M , then N is said to be a *subfactor* of M . One usually assumes that N, M are of type II_1 , i.e. they have dimension 1 (this is just a kind of normalization). Given any such pair, there is a numerical invariant for them known as the (Jones) *index*. This is in fact a generalization of the notion of index for subgroups. The first striking result of Jones is that the index is contained in

$$\{4 \cos^2 \pi/n : n = 3, 4, \dots\} \cup [4, \infty],$$

and that each of these values are realizable. The proof comes about from analysing a 'tower' of type II_1 factors:

$$N \subset M \subset M_1 \subset M_2 \subset \dots,$$

built out of the given pair $N \subset M$ through a repeated application of a method known as the 'basic construction'. This book describes these concepts in detail and the approach is through the notion of bimodules.

In the tower mentioned above, if one looks at relative commutants $\{M_i' \cap M_j : -1 \leq i \leq j\}$ ($M_{-1} = N, M_0 = M$), usually one obtains a grid of finite dimensional von Neumann algebras. But finite dimensional von Neumann algebras are nothing but direct sums of full matrix algebras and their inclusions can be described through certain graphs known as Brattelli diagrams. These graphs become valuable invariants for the factor-subfactor pair one started with. This way, subfactor theory gets transformed into a study of combinatorial and graph theoretic structures. Then the connections with Kronecker's theorem (on norms of matrices with integer entries) and well-known classification of Coxeter graphs and Dynkin diagrams surface naturally.

One can also reverse the process; that is, one can start with special types of combinatorial structures and build new subfactors and analyse them. For instance, one such method known as 'spin models' makes use of complex Hadamard matrices. The last few chapters of this book are devoted to this kind of endeavour. The analysis flavour of von Neumann algebra theory (for example, see classics like Dixmier¹) is completely missing here and it is mostly combinatorics and graph theory. The treatment is quite detailed, but one must admit that the details are quite technical and may enthuse only a specialist.

It is clear that the authors have assumed that the reader is familiar with basics of operator algebra theory on Hilbert spaces; for instance, the introduction to von Neumann algebras given is a little too brief. A good number of clearly stated, interesting examples of factors and subfactors have been provided before building up the whole theory. Missing in the book are the connections with other areas of mathematics, such as low dimensional

topology, algebraic quantum field theory alluded to in the backcover. Except for a short sketch about the relationship with knot theory in the Appendix, no indications are given as to how these other fields come into picture. Perhaps, to learn more about such aspects one should refer to Goodman *et al.*², and Jones³ (surprisingly no reference to this well-written Lecture Notes is to be found in the present book). This book is clearly indispensable for anybody who wants to do research on subfactors. But more importantly this could be very useful to any student or mathematician who wants to get introduced to the subject.

1. Dixmier, J., *von Neumann Algebras*, North Holland, Amsterdam, 1981.
2. Goodman, F., de la Harpe, P., Jones, V., *Coxeter Graphs and Towers of Algebras*, MSRI Publications, Springer, 1989, vol. 14.
3. Jones, V. F. R., *Subfactors and Knots*, CBMS Regional Conference Series in Mathematics, Number 80, American Mathematical Society, 1991.

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The World Wide Web for Scientists & Engineers – A Complete Reference for Navigating, Researching and Publishing Online. Brian J. Thomas. SPIE – The International Society of Optical Engineering, Bellingham, Wash, USA. 1998. ISBN: 0-8194-2775-6. pp. xv + 375. Price \$34.00.

Within a few years of its emergence, the Internet has become an essential part of life for most scientists and engineers. It owes a large part of its phenomenal success and growing popularity to the World Wide Web, the penultimate example of distributed computing, and the data ubiquity the Web has made possible. Thanks to the Web scholars and scientists have evolved new, cost-effective and time saving ways of publishing, disseminating and searching information. Major publishers and information providers have recognized the tremendous potential of the Web – witness *Science Direct* of Elsevier, *Web of Science* of the Institute

for Scientific Information, and the many conferences on electronic publishing – and are experimenting with real time online delivery of information and new pricing models.

Hardly anyone – scientist, engineer or a lay person – ever learns about the Internet and the Web from a book. Most of us learn to point and click our way from site to site through hands on experience and with some help from our colleagues. The Net itself offers much help. But if one wants to acquire mastery over the Net and explore all possibilities on the Web, then one needs the help of an expert. This book by Brian Thomas is one of the best I have come across. The fact that four reputed societies other than SPIE, viz. ASME, IEE, IEEE and SAE, have lent their names as joint publishers is an indication of the importance they attach to the new developments and the quality of the book.

The book is divided into three parts, each dealing with one of three distinct yet closely overlapping areas, viz. essential tools and applications, web authoring and publishing, and searching and researching. Starting with a comprehensive introduction to web technologies and the essential tools for communication, the author moves on to browsers and tells the readers how to leverage one's browser to maximize one's advantage. Then he moves on to providing some in-depth perspectives on electronic publishing in science and engineering and explains the profound implications of 'personal publishing'. This is followed by some down-to-earth instruction on constructing web pages and advanced web publishing. He introduces HTML and other essential technologies, explains the construction of tables, forms, and graphics, and provides guidance on standards and avoiding pitfalls. The author makes a casual mention of XML, which was emerging at the time of writing. Surely, he will write a lot more about it in subsequent editions.

In the final section, the most useful to a very large number of scientists and engineers, the author discusses, with the help of some actual examples, the merits of half a dozen search engines: AltaVista, HotBot, Infoseek, Excite, Lycos and Yahoo. He lists a very large number of selected web sites for 22 fields, running to more than 150 pages. The fields include agriculture, aeronautics, biology, chemistry, computer science, medicine, physics,

and virtual reality. A glossary that has more than 200 entries, a bibliography of selected books and a whole section comparing different search engines add to the value of the book.

On the whole this is a useful book written by an expert. It will certainly help one get the best out of the Web. It is excellent value for money.

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Hotspots of Endemic Plants of India, Nepal and Bhutan. M. P. Nayar. Tropical Botanic Garden and Research Institute, Thiruvananthapuram.

The signing of the Convention of Biodiversity (CBD) has placed a heavy responsibility on the developing countries in the tropical–subtropical–hot temperate belt of the world. This belt has not been affected by the successive glaciations. It has, therefore, remained relatively undisturbed and is very rich in biodiversity. It also harbours Vavilovian Centres of origin and evolution of crop plants.

Although the signing of the CBD was apparently a political event, most of the developing countries did not realize the full implication of what they had *actually* signed. As the story goes, when USA refused to sign CBD, many developing countries, who had signed CBD earlier, had second thoughts and became suspicious as to what they had actually signed. If true, this reflects on the extent and nature of ignorance at the political and administrative levels about CBD in the developing countries. Such an ignorance still prevails even though a country like India is highly respected for its scientific and technical work in biological and agricultural fields. Hardly any country (India included) followed the CBD with an implementable conservation strategy *actually* on the ground.

With the foregoing in mind, the book entitled *Hotspots of Endemic Plants of India, Nepal and Bhutan* by M. P. Nayar is most timely. We are indeed grateful to him for this study and India should use this well-researched document to con-

serve atleast its endemic flora. If appropriate steps are not taken in time, endangerment of such species may lead to their extinction. India has already a sound knowledge base about the hotspots and the endemic plants, but it has not translated it into action. There is need for the following by the nodal departments/ministries:

- Based on well-thought out criteria, prioritization of the endangered species and areas needs to be attempted. A major programme needs to be mounted on the conservation of the prioritized endangered species so as to save these in time and space. This does not mean only cordoning of areas and hoping that these species will be saved, but it means conservation has to be attempted on genetic-evolutionary basis. If this is not done soon, the country will lose some of its distinctive plant wealth.
- A similar exercise needs to be attempted on our endangered animals. Here no doubt some work has been done in the past on mega-animals but it has not followed genetic–evolutionary pathway.
- ZSI in association with Bureaus of Fish and Animal Genetic Resources of the ICAR, needs to put up a well-researched document like that of Nayar on animals.
- A group needs to be identified for microorganism conservation. We have neither any worthwhile knowledge about this wealth nor about its actual loss. This being so notwithstanding the fact that the ICAR has decided to constitute a National Microbial Gene Bank.
- As a follow-up of the good work done by Nayar, the government may seriously consider creating a mechanism to oversee the implementation of the trans-ministerial conservation project on endangered biota of India.

If adequate attention is not paid to these aspects, the country will lose its floristic and faunistic distinctiveness. Being a biomass-dependent country, the biotic wealth is one of its main strengths. The fund of knowledge generated over the years now needs to be used to generate biowealth.

It may also be remembered that at one time the rice cultivation in the entire SE Asian belt was threatened on account of